

ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT FACTORS AND HIGH SPIRITUALITY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article presents information about the importance of spirituality and the role of the concept of spirituality in carrying out democratic reforms in New Uzbekistan. It was mentioned in detail about the essence of spiritual thinking in the upbringing of young people and their development into perfect people in the future. Wide discussions have been held in our country about the opportunities created for our youth and the measures being implemented to make the most of their free time. The essence and quality of our national traditions, national values and our ancient history in improving the spirituality of our youth and raising them to be perfect people have been described. Dear human being in this great country, attention to the future of our motherland is attention to the future of our country, its people, and of course the nation.

Keywords: Spirituality, democratic reforms, future generation, elections, spiritual void, ideology, spiritual heritage, perfect person, education, upbringing, spiritual consciousness, educational programs, national values.

Introduction

Until now, under the slogan "New Uzbekistan", new reforms, reforms, new democratic systems are being implemented in the path of spiritual growth. Many opportunities have been created for the spirituality of our people, as well as for our youth to grow up as perfect people in the future. Based on the initiatives of the President, new reforms were implemented in order to provide quality education to young people in higher education institutions. This is a great respect for our youth, the future generation. These days, in order to improve the spiritual maturity of young people, various competitions and events are held. Existing problems in the economic, social and political spheres of society can be solved by developing spirituality and relying on it. Spirituality is considered an important factor that leads the nation to development and increases the power of the state. Because wherever, in any country, spirituality is at a high level, there, in that country, ignorance, envy, carelessness, selfishness, laziness, arrogance, nonsense, gossip, short-sightedness, There is no place for negative vices such as evil, subversiveness, betrayal of the country and people, slander,

and lack of spirituality. As a result of comprehensive reforms and creative works implemented in our country, the way of thinking of our people is changing. The importance of the life-giving idea "From national revival to national rise" is increasing more and more in the establishment of a legal state and civil society in our country. After our country gained independence, the priority of the state policy was to raise a free-thinking, self-aware, society's goals and interests, fully mature and perfect person. Its implementation requires, first of all, to enrich the internal spirituality of students and to form an independent worldview. Every state, every nation is powerful with its intellectual potential and high spirituality. We need to develop spiritual awareness in our children. Only then will our children become immune to traditional gaps. We put forward the opinion that in order for the education and upbringing of our youth to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap (spiritual gap) to appear in this matter. If a spiritual gap begins to form among our youth, the mental, spiritual and spiritual maturity of our youth will slow down. For this reason, some of our young people are influenced by various unnecessary ideas, and at the same time, it leads to the violation of their moral education, spirituality, and negative psychological effects. Today, the question of forming the spirituality of free citizens in building a new life and foundation of a new society in our country is extremely urgent for us. Under the slogan "Let's build a new Uzbekistan together", a wide range of opportunities have been created for young people to make good use of their free time and achieve their goals. New international educational programs are being used for the education of our youth. Each of us is responsible for the development of our young people into educated, intelligent and spiritually mature people. Therefore, it has been emphasized that we should not be indifferent to the future of our youth. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev declared 2024 as the "Year of supporting youth and business" in the Republic of Uzbekistan. We would not be mistaken if we say that this is a very strong attention to the education and upbringing of our youth, to their health, and to the development of spiritually mature people. These opportunities are recognized as a great respect for the spiritual growth of our youth. Currently, based on the reforms of modern educational programs, several changes have been made in the educational processes of schools and preschool educational institutions. In forming the spirituality of our youth, our nation, and our people, the highest priorities are to improve their outlook and thinking. In our country, since time immemorial, among our people, it is appropriate to inculcate the idea that destructive ideas will never come from educated, spiritual and enlightened,

educated, perfect people. It is our main duty to educate our youth in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, people, and nation. We need to form the spiritual maturity of young people and instill in them our national traditions, national values and ancient history. We can understand from the words of our grandfather Abdulla Awlani that "Education is a matter of life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster for us." The builders of tomorrow's future of every nation and people are the young, mature generation of this country. This requires that education and upbringing work be carried out in harmony. Education cannot be separated from education, and education cannot be separated from education - this is an oriental view, an oriental philosophy of life. It can be said that the main goal of the modern educational program is to achieve the formation of each person as a spiritually mature, perfect, spiritually rich and mature person with high human qualities. One of the most important areas of education is ideological education. The strategic priority tasks based on the secondary education program are aimed at inculcating national ideas on the basis of the national-cultural and spiritual-ethical traditions of the people, national values and democratic principles. It is a source of ideological-cultural, spiritual-pedagogical and other influence measures aimed at forming all-round spiritually mature individuals. Moral education, which is considered the main tool in raising a perfect person, is of great importance, thanks to which a person's moral qualities, high moral consciousness, and moral behavior are formed. The task of aesthetic education is to develop the creative abilities of young people in the fields of music, literature, painting, and theater. It is reasonable to believe that the essence of spirituality is very important in strengthening democratic reforms and strategic reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Many opportunities and conditions have been created for young people in our country. We must use these terms wisely and correctly. All nations and peoples of our country care about the future of young people. The reason is that the future of the country, the future of the country, is definitely the youth. Therefore, along with the children's parents, their teachers, community activists, and intellectuals, we also need to pay attention to the spiritual development, education and upbringing of the youth. We should help young people to grow up to become mature and perfect people, to become experienced professionals of their profession. Education begins first of all with the family. As soon as a child is born in the family, parents begin to form the roots of education. It can be concluded that the President has high confidence in the youth. Until now, "Agency for Youth Affairs" was established to solve youth

problems. In each neighborhood, interest-free loans were allocated for our youth to engage in entrepreneurship. At the same time, fertile plots of land are being allocated to young people for horticulture. It is safe to say that such strategic reforms will have an effect on the effective use of free time by young people and their place in society. The main goal of organizing such democratic reforms and the strategic priorities aimed at young people are the formation of the spiritual thinking and spiritual consciousness of all young people, their development as a perfect person in the future, and the development of a mature specialist in their profession. consists of will consist of educating lib. First of all, we should encourage young people to glorify our national values, honor our national history and ancestors, honor our national cultural traditions, and preserve our spiritual and educational heritage. As long as we live in an independent and great country, a free and prosperous country must remain. In this holy land, human dignity and the future of young people are seen as the main task.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that the place of spirituality in the implementation of democratic reforms in New Uzbekistan is incomparable. All the measures implemented in order to provide quality education to our youth through modern educational programs are for our youth, who are the creators of our future. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to their lives when raising our young people to become mature people. We are happy about the opportunities created for the young generation. Our youth should be happy that they were born in this blessed country and that they are growing up in this beautiful country. We should be proud that Uzbekistan is a child of this country. Uzbekistan is a great country, the future of a great country will certainly be great. The confidence of the Uzbek people, the nation, and the President in the youth is very high. To justify this trust, of course, is in the hands of young people.

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